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Comparative Study of the Germination Power and Growth in the Nursery of Two Varieties of Oil Palm in Grand-Lahou (Côte d'Ivoire)

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Abstract

Oil palm is a plant cultivated for its high oil content and its many benefits for humans. To this end, a comparison study of the germination power and growth in the nursery of the oil palm was even carried out at the PALMCI Grand-Lahou nursery. The sprouted seeds of the oil palm come from two different varieties, one of which is local; the CNRA variety and the other PALMELIT variety of Beninese origin. Parameters such as emergence rate, mortality rate, and caterpillar attacks were evaluated. Growth measures based on the number of leaves, leaf length, leaf width, neck circumference as well as height were evaluated.

The results showed that in the nursery, the CNRA variety exhibits the best morphological and physiological parameters than the PALMELIT variety. However, studies from planting to harvest and evaluation of biochemical and nutritional parameters are recommended.

Keywords: Oil palm, Nursery, Variety, Growth parameters, Physiological parameters.

INTRODUCTION

The oil palm or *Elaeis guineensis* Jacq is a monocotyledonous perennial plant of the Arecaceae family. Through these different virtues, it plays an essential role in the life of the populations of Africa and elsewhere. It is cultivated for its fruits (in cooking for sauces) and its seeds rich in oil for food use (margarine, frying, ice cream etc.), industrial (cosmetics, ink etc.) and used in oleochemistry, as biofuel (Sudram *et al.*, 2003). The fruits of the palm tree produce two oils. The first is palm oil, extracted from the pulp of the fruit, and in recent years has become the leading source of vegetable fats on the world market. The second is palm kernel oil, extracted from the kernel seeds, authorized in the European Union as a substitute for cocoa butter (Jacquemard, 2012).

Today Indonesia and Malaysia are the world's leading oil producers, and together account for over 85 % of production compared to just 6 % for Africa. The oil palm sector positions Côte d'Ivoire ninth in the world and second on the African continent after Nigeria, with an Ivorian production of palm bunches of 1,800,000 tonnes (including 1,000,000 tonnes from village plantations) with a production of 1,800,000 tonnes. 420,000 ton crude oil. This palm oil production represents 3.1 % of Ivorian GDP (Kodo, 2018).

Indeed, introduced in Côte d'Ivoire as an industrial crop around 1920 (CNRA, 2004), the palm tree will experience effective development thanks to the two palm plans (1963-1985 and 1985-1990) initiated by the Ivorian government in the framework for the diversification of export crops. This is how the companies for the development of this sector are created: SODEPALM, PALMINDUSTRIE and PALMIVOIRE. After the liberalization of the sector, three new private companies were created. These are the PALM-CI, SIPEF-CI and PALMAFRIQUE which will appropriate the heritage of these first three (Ricardo, 2010). In 2015, the ambitious Côte d'Ivoire decided to implement a third Ivorian oil palm plan (2015-2025), it aims to triple production in order to cope with the booming world market (Fages, 2019). These projections for increased demand are attracting envy and several countries now want to take their place in the industry to take advantage of this windfall (Index, 2014). In order to meet this strong local and global demand, the introduction of a new tested variety that performs better in other countries is needed. In this research, the

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PALMELIT variety which has already proved its worth in Benin interested PALMCI. The introduction of this new variety should be the subject of a comparative study with local varieties. For this purpose, the PALMELIT variety is compared to the local variety CNRA.

The general objective of this study is therefore to compare the germination power and growth in the nursery of the CNRA and PALMELIT varieties.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study zone

The UAI of Irobo is located in the department of Grand-Lahou, 105 km from the city of Abidjan (Figure 1). It straddles two departments that are Grand-Lahou in the West and Jacqueville in the East.

Its geographical location is 5° and 5°30' North latitude and 4°30' and 5° West longitude. The relief not very broken and marked in the west by hills, mammellings, talwegs and poorly drained lowlands. To the south, the lagoon, maritime landscape and a sandy coast. The soils are clay-sandy types suitable for market gardening, food crops and perennial crops such as oil palm cultivation.

The climate, hot and rainy, of the Attiéen type is characterized by:

- The abundance of precipitation with an average rainfall of 3000 to 3980.5 mm / year;
- high atmospheric humidity (annual average 85 %);
- an average temperature varies between 23 °C and 31 °C per year;
- low thermal amplitudes (less than 5 °C)
- sunshine, the duration of which varies on average between 1500 and 2000 hours / year.

The rainfall regime is unevenly distributed over the year. The periods from January to mid-February and from August to early August to September are characterized by very low rainfall with an average of 22 to 213 mm of rain per month. From the beginning of March, the amount of rain per month gradually increases until reaching a maximum of 621 mm of rain in June before decreasing in July. The period from October to December is also marked by an abundance of rain (Kadio, 2008).

The UAI of Irobo has a nursery site, that of Tamabo, which is the subject of our study. Tamabo is a village 12 km from Irobo. UAI Irobo has opted for the direct nursery method. The Tamabo nursery covers an area of 10 ha. Its objective is the production of plants intended for industrial and village plantations. It has existed since 1992. An irrigation system supplied by a stream 1 km from the nursery, using a motorized pump and an irrigation system (filter, valves, booms, sprinklers) by sprinkling well disposed.

Figure 1: location of the study area

Materiel

Plant material

The plant material used in this study consists of sprouted oil palm seeds of different origins (Figure 2). One from Côte d'Ivoire more precisely from the Mé station of the CNRA called "CNRA germinated seed" hybrid C1001F and the other from Benin called "PALMELIT germinated seeds" hybrid C1001Fg.

A: CNRA Germinated seed

B: PALMELIT Germinated seed

Figure 2: Plant material presentation

Technical equipment

All the technical equipment used for setting up this experiment is as follows: Machetes were used to weed the land, picket cables made up of a long rope separated by small strings marking the distances between the plants and the stakes were used for the picketing. A tape measure and markers were used to take the measurements. For irrigation, a system composed of a sprinkler and ramps were used to irrigate the plants. The rain gauge was used to measure the depth of water (rainwater, water supplied) received by the plants. The maintenance of the tracks on the plot was done at the Dabas.

Methods

Experimental apparatus

The trial took place over six months, from November 2019 to May 2020. November was devoted to setting up the trial. The transplanting of the germinated seeds (CNRA and PALMELIT) was done in December. The measurements were taken from February until May 2020. The experimental setup is a file block with three repetitions. The basic plot is 60 m wide, made up of 500 plants. The seedlings are staggered and the distance between it's seedlings is 0.6 m. On the plot, the plants form diagonals. The measurements were taken on controls at a frequency of 1/50 for each plot, therefore 10 controls for one plot. The distance between 2 elementary plots is 1m. The distance between two blocks is 4 m. The experiment converse a total area of 2912 m² (Figure 3).

Implementation of the culture

The site was previously weeded (manually or chemically), and the staking was done in staggered rows. The bags (40 x 40 cm) were filled with potting soil (substrates) previously sieved. After staking, the filled bags are placed in place of the stakes, so as to have diagonals over the entire plot. The potting soil is disinfected with bleach (1 liter of bleach per 10 liter of water) or with fungicide and herbicide two weeks before transplanting the germinated seeds. They underwent abundant watering before transplanting. The transplanting of the seed was done so as to have the rootlet downwards and the stem upwards. The seed was transplanted at least 1 cm from the substrate (upwards). After transplanting, the bags containing the seeds were watered. Transplanting was carried out on the same day, block by block, variety by variety. CNRA variety and PALMELIT variety.

Maintenance

Maintenance of the plot was carried out according to several activities. Weeding, which is done manually inside the bags every two weeks, depending on the rate of grass cover. The manual weeding was carried out between the rows and on the tracks, the raising, it took place when the plants reached a stage because it allows to fix the plants well.

Figure 3: Experimental apparatus

Data collection

Data collection was carried out in two stages, on observable data and on measurable data.

Lifting Rate (LR)

After transplanting the germinated seeds, the rate of emergence was determined. It consisted of counting the sachets where the leaf appeared. This rate is defined according to the formula:

$$LR = \frac{\text{Number of lifted plants(NLP)}}{\text{Number of transplanted plants (NTP)}} * 100$$

Infestation index (RxPA)

The health of the plants was observed throughout the experiment. The attacks that occurred during this attempt are caterpillar attacks. The caterpillars attack the leaves of plants and leave visible spots as they pass. Thus the percentage of plants attacked (**RxPA**) translates into the number of plants attacked (**NPA**) out of the total number of plants (**TNP**) is determined by the following formula:

$$RxPA = \frac{\text{Number of plant attacked (NPA)}}{\text{Total number of plant (TNP)}} * 100$$

Mortality rate

It was followed throughout the experiment. The mortality rate (MR) is expressed by the number of dead plants (NDP) over the total number of plants (TNP) and is determined by the following formula:

$$MR = \frac{\text{Number of dead plant (NDP)}}{\text{total number of plant (TNP)}} * 100$$

Number of leaves

On each control plant, the number of leaves was counted. The leaves taken into account are the functional leaves, leaves with the characteristics of a good leaf. That is, its leaves are dark green in color, well deployed and they creak.

Leaves length

Leaves length was measured on the last functional leaves. The leaves length was taken from the petiole to the top of the leaves, in centimeters.

Leaves width

The width was also taken from the last functional leaf of the plant. The width measurement was made in the middle part of the sheet, horizontally in centimeters.

Plant circumference

The circumference was measured at the collar of the plant that is to say at the base of the plant in centimeters.

Plants height

The width was also taken from the last functional leaf of the plant. The width measurement was made in the middle part of the sheet, horizontally in centimeters.

Statistical analysis

Two analyzes with one classification criterion (ANOVA 1) were carried out with the software R. version 3.1. In order to evaluate the vegetative variables according to the palm variety and the growth of the vegetative variables over time. When a significant difference was noted between the factors for a given variable, multiple comparisons were made using the least significant difference (ppds) test. The significance of the test was determined by comparing the probability (P) associated with the test statistic to the theoretical value $\alpha = 0.05$ (Dagnelie, 1998).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Results****Pest lifting, mortality and resistance rates**

The lifting rate, mortality after transplanting and also the monitoring of pest attack for the varieties CNRA and PALMELIT is compared in Table I. Analysis of this table shows that the variety CNRA has a slightly higher lifting rate (89.87 %) than the variety PALMELIT (89.74 %). This observation is confirmed by the high mortality rate (6.66 %) for the PALMELIT variety against (3.33 %) for the CNRA variety. In addition, observation of this table shows that the PALMELIT variety was more attacked by caterpillars (26.66 %) compared to (20 %) for the CNRA variety.

Table I: Comparison of lifting, mortality and attack rates by variety

Indices \ Variety	CNRA	PALMELIT
Lifting Rate (%)	89,87	89,74
Mortality rate (%)	3,33	6,66
Caterpillar Attack (%)	20	26,66

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Evaluation of growth parameters

Number of leaves

The number of leaves as a function of time is shown in Figure 4. Analysis of this histogram shows that there is no significant difference in the number of leaves. For the first and fourth month, the number of leaves is practically identical between the variety CNRA and the variety PALMELIT.

* Histograms followed by the same letters are not significantly different.

Figure 4: Number of leaves according to months

Leaf width

Figure 5 shows the comparative study of the change in leaf width of the two varieties "CNRA and PALMELIT" over time. The observation of this figure shows that during the first three months of the observation, there is no significant difference between the variety CNRA and the variety PALMELIT. The leaf width during the first three months is practically identical for the two varieties studied. However by the fourth month, there is no significant difference between the two varieties. The leaf width of the CNRA variety is much greater than that of the PALMELIT variety.

* Histograms followed by the same letters are not significantly different.

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Figure 5: leaves width according to time

Leaf length

The histogram in Figure 6 shows the comparative evolution in leaf length over time between the variety CNRA and the variety PALMELIT. During the observation time, the leaf length of the CNRA variety showed a significant difference compared to the PALMELIT variety. The leaf length of the CNRA variety during the nursery is significantly higher than that of the PALMELIT variety.

* Histograms followed by the same letters are not significantly different

Figure 6: Leaves length according to time

Plants height

The comparative study of the height of the plants in the nursery of the CNRA and PALMELIT variety is presented in figure 7. The analysis of the histograms of months 1 to month 4 shows that there is a significant difference between the heights of the plants at the level of both varieties. Growth in height in the nursery of the CNRA variety is stronger than that of the PALMELIT variety during the 4 months of measurement in the nursery.

* Histograms followed by the same letters are not significantly different.

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Figure 7: Plants heights according to months

Circumference of plants

The circumference of the plants of the CNRA and PALMELIT varieties is compared by the histograms in Figure 8. The change in the circumference of the plants during the first month, second month and fourth month is not significantly different. On the other hand, in the third month, there is a significant difference for this growth parameter between the variety CNRA and the variety PALMELIT. In general, the circumference of plants of the PALMELIT variety is lower than the CNRA.

* Histograms followed by the same letters are not significantly different

Figure 8: Circumference of plants according to months

Comparison of growth parameters depending on the variety during the experimentation phase

The various parameters studied for the CNRA and PALMELIT variety are compared in Table II. The comparison of the number of leaves, the width of the leaves, as well as that of the length of the leaves but also of the height and the circumference of the plants in nursery shows significant differences for some growth parameters and non-significant differences for other parameters. In fact, for the length of the leaves and the height of the plants, $P < 0.001$ shows that there is a significant difference between the variety CNRA and the variety PALMELIT. The CNRA variety has an average of around 17.488 ± 5.389 compared to 14.061 ± 5.295 for the PALMELIT variety. For the height of the plants, the averages for the PALMELIT and CNRA varieties are respectively about 23.332 ± 9.325 and 26.853 ± 9.471 . Regarding the other parameters, there is no significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

Table II: Evolution of growth parameters according to the palm variety

Variétés	Nombre de feuilles	Largeur de feuille	Longueur de feuille	Hauteur de plante	Circonférence plante
PALMELIT	5,518±2,688 ^a	3,105±1,642 ^a	14,061±5,295 ^b	23,332±9,325 ^b	3,657±2,508 ^a
CNRA	5,796±2,758 ^a	3,235±1,398 ^a	17,488±5,389 ^a	26,853±9,471 ^a	4,028±2,478 ^a
F	1,094	0,349	45,559	105,405	2,227
P	0,296	0,555	0,001	0,001	0,137

*Averages followed by the same letters are not significantly different

Discussion

The comparison of the CNRA and PALMELIT varieties was made based on different morphological parameters namely the number of leaves, the length of the leaf, the width of the leaf, the height of the plant, and the circumference of the crown. As well as physiological processes such as lifting rate, mortality rate and caterpillar attacks.

The CNRA and PALMELIT variety exhibited a substantially identical lifting rate. It is 89.87 % for the CNRA variety and 89.74 % for the PALMELIT variety. The pest resistance rate shows a slight difference of 20 % for CNRAs against 26 % for PALMELIT. On the other hand, with regard to the mortality rate, in CNRAs (3.33 %) is the double observed in PALMELIT (6.66 %). This observation may be justified by the fact that the CNRA variety is a local variety and therefore adapted to climatic conditions. Indeed, the CNRA variety comes from the CNRA experimental field located on the road to Dabou, a locality in the Côte d'Ivoire. While the PALMELIT variety comes from the experimental field of Pobé locality of Benin. This locality of Benin, according to Azontonde (1991) and Aholoukpè (2013), is an area of average rainfall (1300 mm) and which often experiences climatic disturbances and very marked water deficits in the dry season. On the other hand, the coastal area of Côte d'Ivoire from which the CNRA variety comes has a rainfall of 1800 mm well distributed throughout the year and favorable to the cultivation of oil palm (N'guettia & Kamagate, 2010). It is therefore this difference in agroecological factors that would be the basis of the agromorphological differences. These results are consistent with those obtained by Boyé *et al.* (2016) during their studies on the diversity of cowpea varieties in Côte d'Ivoire. According to these authors, there is a reduction in the agromorphological characteristics of cowpea due to the low rainfall and the short rainy season as well as the high temperatures and the intensity of the long dry season. Kouassi *et al.* (2018) have also shown that the accumulation of reserves in seeds in cowpeas depends on climatic factors. However, authors like Aly *et al.* (2017), showed that a new variety could adapt to local climatic conditions. They worked on the evaluation and participatory selection of improved cowpea varieties in rural areas in the Couffo department in Benin. They introduced five varieties from Burkina Faso which they compared to the local variety from Benin. The improved variety K VX 421-2J from Burkina Faso exhibited the best grain yield of 1065 kg / ha and a high biomass yield of 1735 kg / ha. Attacks by caterpillars in the nursery concern both the PALMELIT variety and the local variety CNRA. However, the introduced variety was more attacked by caterpillars. This observation can be explained by the fact that the local variety has a certain level of tolerance to caterpillars. N'Zi *et al.* (2010) found an identical result. Their study was even on the evolution of populations of *Bemisia tabaci* on varieties of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum L.*) in central Côte d'Ivoire. Five varieties of tomatoes were compared, only the local control had fairly good and better performance in terms of contamination. These results are in contradiction with those of Muwo *et al.* (2018) who worked on the evaluation of the production of five varieties of hot pepper (*Capsicum sp.*) under the agroecological conditions of the Batéké Plateau in Kinshasa. They showed that the severity of the variegation was 90 % in the local variety and 70 % in the introduced varieties. It is important to note that this oil palm nursery study did not report on all caterpillar attacks, diseases and all the major pests of palm tree nurseries. Jacquemard (2012) to enumerate diseases such as ganoderma, defoliating caterpillars: Caterpillars of *Thosea vestuta*, caterpillar of *Metissa plana*, *Rhinoceros orytes* which present a danger for the culture of the palm tree in nursery. The agrophysiological parameters were evaluated. Certain parameters such as the number of leaves, the width of the leaf, and the circumference of the plant did not show any significant difference. However, others such as leaf length and plant height showed significant differences. The average number of leaves is approximately the same for the two varieties. These results are identical with those of authors such as Gray (1969) and Breure (1987). These authors have shown that in the palm tree the rate of leaf emissions calculated on average over the year is one leaf every 17 days or so or 22 leaves per year under Mé conditions. It is also approved by Chang *et al.* (1988) who obtained 21 to 22 leaves per year in Malaysia and 23 leaves per year in Guinea. According to Jacquemard & Baudoin (1987), at 9 months, a plant when it comes out of the nursery must have the crown measure of between 18 and 22 cm. At the end of the observations in the nursery, the circumference of the collar is between 3 and 13 cm for the CNRA and between 3 and 11 cm for the PALMELIT. The two varieties are in the range set by these authors. The results indicate that the height growth of palm nursery plants appears to be influenced by the origin of

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the germinated seeds. Evidenced by the low height of PALMELIT compared to the local variety. At this 5 month stage, the CNRA plants are getting closer to reality than the PALMELIT. According to the standards set by some authors such as Ewane, (2018) and Jacquemard *et al.* (2008), a palm tree at 9 months must have a height of 0.6 to 1m.

However at 5 months the CNRA were between 14 and 49 cm, during this time the PALMELIT are between 19 and 38 cm. The variability observed in the height of the plants would therefore result from the difference in their ability to adapt to the environment and the environment in which they were tested. Several authors Tristant (2017); Jacquemard *et al.* (1981) have already indicated that this trait is sufficiently heritable to promote effective choices on the self-worth of parents and their descendants. The work of Fondio *et al.*, (2013) on the evaluation of the agronomic performances of nine varieties of tomato also showed that the difference observed in the growth of various varieties of tomato would be related to their genotype and to the environment in which they have been tested.

CONCLUSION

This study made it possible to compare two varieties of germinated oil palm seeds CNRA and PALMELIT under the same environmental conditions and having undergone the same treatments (irrigation, inputs, etc.). Parameters and measurements were taken and observed at the same stage of development. The results of this study reveal that the various morphological and physiological parameters evaluated on these sprouted seeds of different origin present significant differences for others. For morphological parameters such as, the height, the plants of the CNRA variety have an average of 26.853 ± 9.471 and the plants of PALMELIT are at 23.332 ± 9.325 . For the length, 14.061 ± 5.295 for the PALMELIT against 17.488 ± 5.389 for the CNRA. The width, circumference and number of sheets do not show a significant difference. However, plants of the CNRA variety in the nursery exhibit significantly better growth parameters. In terms of physiological parameters such as the lifting rate, it is almost identical for the two varieties, the mortality rate of PALMELIT is double that of CNRA and attacks by PALMELIT caterpillars high compared to CNRAs.

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